

Studies on Some Mixed Schiffbase Complexes : Part III

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Preparation and properties of some mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' , where $M = Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$; $LH = 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde$ and $L'H = 2-OH-benzophenone$ or its methyl derivatives are described. MLL' on being treated with ammonia, ethylenediamine or propylenediamine result in the formation of mixed Schiffbase complexes. Transimination reaction of mixed imine Schiffbase complexes with ethylenediamine or propylenediamine have also been studied. The structure of the complexes have been discussed on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic moments, infrared, nmr and electronic spectral data.

COMPLEXES of the type ML_2 , where $LH =$ salicylaldehyde or 2-OH-phenones and their reactions with amines leading to the formation of the schiffbase complexes have been studied earlier¹⁻⁷. Reactions have also been performed on the Schiffbase in complexes⁸. The possibility of the formation of mixed Schiffbase complexes of different N-substituted bis(salicylalimine) $Ni(II)$ complexes has been indicated by Chakravorty and Holm⁹ on the basis of NMR studies. Such complexes have, however, not been isolated in solid state. Recently mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' , where $LH =$ salicylaldehyde and $L'H = 2-OH-acetophenone$ or its methyl derivatives or $LH =$ salicylaldehyde and $L'H = 2-OH-benzophenone$ or its methyl derivatives and their reactions with amines leading to the formation of mixed schiffbase complexes have been reported^{10,11}. The present study is concerned with the preparation, reactions and characterization of a series of mixed ligand complexes of general formula MLL' , where $M = Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$, $LH = 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde$ and $L'H = 2-OH-benzophenone$ or its methyl derivatives(I).

where $M = Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$, and $X = H, 4-CH_3$ or $5-CH_3$. Compound(I) on treatment with ammonia forms mixed imine Schiffbase complex(II).

The mixed imine Schiffbase complexes(II) have also been prepared by treating the metal ammonia complexes with one equivalent each of 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde and another of 2-OH-benzophenone or its methyl derivatives(II) where $M = Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$ and $X = H, 4-CH_3$ or $5-CH_3$. Treatments of complexes(I) and (II) with ethylenediamine (en) or propylenediamine (pn) result in the formation of new Schiffbase complexes with the diamine condensed at one end with 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde and at the other end with 2-OH-benzophenone or its methyl derivatives (III) where $R = H$ or CH_3 .

Experimental

Material used :

2-OH-benzophenone and its methyl derivatives were prepared and recrystallised from absolute alcohol¹². All the complexes were prepared in non aqueous medium. The salts used were nickel nitrate and cupric chloride of analar grade.

Method and apparatus :

TLC analysis were done on silica gel G (Sichem) using chloroform+ether (5 : 3) mixture as the solvent. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were

determined at room temperature by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 427 Infrared Grating Spectrophotometer. NMR spectra of the complexes in CDCl_3 were recorded on a Perkin Elmer R.32 NMR Spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the complexes in chloroform were taken on a DU-2 Beckman Spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cell in the range 300 nm to 1000 nm.

Preparation of the complexes :

1. [2-OH-1-naphthaldehydato-2-OH-benzophenonato]Cu(II) :

This complex was prepared by adding 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g) and 2-OH-benzophenone (1.98 g) dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 ml) to the alcoholic solution of copper(II) chloride (1.70 g). The reaction was carried out at a lower temperature by using a freezing mixture. The pH was raised to 5 by adding ammonia solution and the mixture was stirred well. The reaction mixture was filtered and the compound was washed with hot water and alcohol. The solubility of the compound is very low and hence it could not be recrystallised.

2. [2-OH-1-naphthaldehydato-2-OH-benzophenonato]Ni(II) :

This complex was obtained at $\text{pH} \sim 5$ by adding 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g) and 2-OH-benzophenone (1.98 g) dissolved in absolute ethanol (30 ml) to alcoholic solution of nickel nitrate (2.90 g) at 0° . It was stirred well. The reaction mixture was filtered, washed with hot water and alcohol. It could not be recrystallised because the solubility was very low.

3. [2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-benzophenonimine]Cu(II) or Ni(II) :

The above complexes were prepared by two methods :

(a) The preformed mixed ligand complexes of Cu(II) (2 g) or Ni(II) (2 g) were taken in suspension in ethanol (25 ml) and treated with excess of ammonia (50 ml) and refluxed (4 hr.). It was filtered, washed with hot water, alcohol and dried. The compound could be recrystallised from chloroform solution.

(b) Alcoholic solution of 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g) and 2-OH-benzophenone (1.98 g) were added to Cu(II) or Ni(II) amine complex. Cu(II) or Ni(II) amine complexes were prepared by the addition of ammonia (50 ml) to copper(II) chloride (1.70 g) or nickel(II) nitrate (2.90 g). The reaction mixture was refluxed (4 hr.) with stirring when solid separated out. It was filtered, washed and dried. It was recrystallized from chloroform solution.

4. N-N'-ethylene[2-OH-1-naphthalaldimino-2-OH-benzophenonimine]Cu(II) or Ni(II) :

These Schiffbase complexes were prepared directly and by amine exchange method.

In the first method, preformed mixed ligand Cu(II) or Ni(II) complexes (2 g) were taken in suspension in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed (5 hr) with en (2 ml) or pn (2 ml). The solid which separated out was filtered, washed with hot water, alcohol, dried and recrystallized from chloroform.

The diamine Schiffbase complexes were also obtained by transimination reaction. The preformed mixed imine Schiffbase complex of Cu(II) or Ni(II) (2 g) was taken in suspension in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed (5 hr) with en (2 ml) or pn (2 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred well to obtain the compound. It was filtered, washed with water and alcohol, dried and recrystallized from chloroform.

Complexes of the substituted benzophenones were prepared in the same way as detailed above.

Some general properties of the complexes :

The complexes are coloured and sufficiently stable at room temperature. The Schiffbase complexes are unstable in acids. All the complexes are insoluble in water. The Schiffbase complexes are soluble in chloroform.

Results and Discussion

TLC analysis of all the complexes were done using a mixture of chloroform+ether (5 : 3) as the solvent. This solvent was selected after trying several solvents in the TLC analysis of a 1 : 1 mixture of bis(2-OH-1-naphthalaldimine)M(II) and bis(2-OH-benzophenonimine)M(II) complexes. Chloroform solution of the

TABLE—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES AND MIXED SCHIFFBASE COMPLEXES

No.	Name of the Complex	Colour	Metal%		Nitrogen%		λ_{max} nm in CHCl ₃	ϵ	μ_{eff} in B.M.
			Exptd.	Obtd.	Exptd.	Obtd.			
1.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldihydato-2-OH-benzophenonato) Cu(II)	Yellowish Green	14.72	15.10	—	—	640	—	1.98
2.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-benzophenonimine) Cu(II)	Olivegreen	14.79	14.47	6.52	6.20	540	110	1.93
3.	N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-benzophenoniminato) Cu(II)	Greenish Gray	13.95	13.59	6.15	6.33	550	510	2.10
4.	N-N'-propylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-benzophenoniminato) Cu(II)	Gray	13.53	13.75	5.96	5.92	545	512	1.99
5.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldihydato-2-OH-benzophenonato) Ni(II)	Greenish yellow	13.76	13.51	—	—	630	—	3.09
6.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-benzophenonimine) Ni(II)	Yellowish red	13.82	13.53	6.59	6.58	540	300	1.06
7.	N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-benzophenoniminato) Ni(II)	„	13.02	12.82	6.21	6.40	550	351	1.13
8.	N-N'-propylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-benzophenoniminato) Ni(II)	„	12.63	12.31	6.03	6.01	530	342	1.14
9.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldehydato-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenonato) Cu(II)	Yellowish green	14.26	13.85	—	—	650	—	2.10
10.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenonimine) Cu(II)	Olive green	14.33	14.07	6.31	6.36	560	117	1.81
11.	N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenoniminato) Cu(II)	Greenish gray	13.53	13.30	5.96	5.30	550	383	1.95
12.	N-N'-propylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenoniminato) Cu(II)	Gray	13.14	12.90	5.79	6.03	545	396	1.86
13.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldihydato-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenonato) Ni(II)	Greenish yellow	13.32	13.08	—	—	610	—	2.94
14.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenonimine) Ni(II)	Yellowish red	13.38	13.12	6.38	5.86	560	182	1.97
15.	N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenoniminato) Ni(II)	„	12.63	12.80	6.03	6.15	560	325	1.27
16.	N-N'-propylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-4-Me-benzophenoniminato) Ni(II)	„	12.26	12.50	5.85	5.75	550	294	1.33
17.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldihydato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenonato) Cu(II)	Yellowish green	14.26	13.90	—	—	640	95	2.10
18.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenonimine) Cu(II)	Olive green	14.33	13.96	6.31	6.37	530	134	1.80
19.	N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenoniminato) Cu(II)	Greenish gray	13.53	13.32	5.96	5.96	540	438	1.91
20.	N-N'-propylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenoniminato) Cu(II)	Gray	13.14	12.80	5.79	5.92	550	420	1.93
21.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldihydato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenonato) Ni(II)	Greenish yellow	13.32	13.31	—	—	540 620	—	3.03
22.	(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenonimine) Ni(II)	Yellowish red	13.38	13.05	6.38	6.19	560	248	0.98
23.	N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenoniminato) Ni(II)	Yellowish red	12.63	12.21	6.03	5.93	545	258	Dia- magnetic
24.	N-N'-propylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenoniminato) Ni(II)	Yellowish red	12.26	12.01	5.85	5.89	550	320	1.50

complexes were taken to put the spot on the chromatographic plates. When the above solvent was used, two spots were obtained, indicating that the two components have distinct R_f values. The mixed ligand complexes, however, showed only one spot with the same solvent. The R_f value of the mixed complexes is intermediate between the two corresponding bis complexes. This shows that the mixed complex is pure and a single compound rather than the mixture of the bis complexes of the two ligands. The R_f values of the complexes are given below. Set I (a) Bis(benzophenonimine) Ni(II)—0.79, (b) (2-OH-1-naphthaldimine-2-OH-benzophenonimine)Ni(II)—0.85, (c) Bis(2-OH-1-naphthaldimine) Ni(II)—0.91. Set II (a) N-N'-ethylene bis(benzophenoniminato)Ni(II)—0.72, (b) N-N'-ethylene(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-benzophenoniminato)Ni(II)—0.75, (c) N-N'-ethylene bis(2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato)Ni(II)—0.78.

The metal and nitrogen contents in the complexes were determined and are presented in the table.

Structure of Cu(II) complexes :

All of the Cu(II) complexes are paramagnetic showing the presence of one unpaired electron. The excess over the expected spin only value found for the present complexes can be attributed to spin orbit coupling.¹³ The spectra of the Cu(II) mixed ligand complexes (1, 9 and 17) are similar and show a peak around ~ 640 nm ($\epsilon = 95$). These complexes may have distorted octahedral structure due to polymerization. The Cu(II) imine Schiffbase complexes show a band around ~ 550 nm ($\epsilon = 134$) and en and pn Schiffbase complexes exhibit a band at ~ 550 nm ($\epsilon = 420$). This shows that the Schiffbase complexes may have square planar structure. The displacement of the band to lower wavelength in Schiffbase complexes indicates formation of a stronger M-N bond.¹⁴ The higher extinction coefficient in the en or pn Schiffbase complexes indicate that the nitrogen atoms are in cis position resulting in structures without centre of symmetry.

Structure of Ni(II) complexes :

The mixed ligand Ni(II) complexes (5, 13 and 21) are paramagnetic with μ around ~ 3.1 . The absorption spectra show bands at ~ 540 nm and ~ 620 nm. From the consideration that ν_2/ν_1 is nearly 1.5, the third band can be expected at ~ 930 nm.¹⁵ This is characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry. This is due to polymerization as observed in bis salicylaldehyde and bis ketonic complexes.^{16,17} Due to very small solubility of these complexes, molar absorbance could not be determined. The Schiffbase complexes obtained are weakly paramagnetic. All the complexes were recrystallised till constant magnetic susceptibility was obtained. Anomalous magnetic behaviour of Ni(II) Schiffbase complexes have been studied and interpreted in detail earlier.^{18,19} The paramagnetism observed may be due to polymerization.^{19,20} The visible spectra of the complexes show a shoulder at ~ 545 nm with $\epsilon = 248$ for the imine complexes and $\epsilon = \sim 300$ for the en and pn Schiffbase

complexes. The band at ~ 400 nm ($\epsilon = 3840$) could be a charge transfer band. This shows that the complexes are square planar in solution. The spectra are comparable with those of the bis schiff-base complexes of Ni(II), reported earlier.¹⁴

In the IR spectrum of [2-OH-1-naphthaldehydato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenonato]Ni(II), the band in the range 3400 cm^{-1} is absent indicating that the -OH hydrogen is lost on coordination. The band at 1640 cm^{-1} corresponds to the aldehydic or ketonic C = O stretching vibration. The displacement is due to coordination. This band disappears and a new band at 1620 cm^{-1} appears in the Schiffbase complexes. This is due to the C = N stretching mode and indicates the formation of the Schiffbase complexes. In the imine Schiffbase complexes(II) the band at 3300 cm^{-1} corresponds to NH stretching frequency. This band is absent in the en and pn Schiffbase complexes(III).

NMR spectrum of the mixed propylenediamine complex, N-N'-propylene[2-OH-1-naphthaldiminato-2-OH-5-Me-benzophenoniminato]Ni(II) shows signals at 8.2τ . This corresponds to methyl protons. The signal is a multiple one because of the presence of the methyl group attached to aliphatic chain and the methyl group of the aromatic ring. The signal between $5.8-6.1\tau$ corresponds to methylene group. The signal at 2.5τ corresponds to the -N = C-H protons of the coordinated naphthaldimine part of the Schiffbase. The NMR spectra of other complexes could not be obtained because they are less soluble, in CDCl_3 or CHCl_3 .

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References

1. H. SCHIFF, *Ann.*, 1869, 150, 193.
2. ETTLING, *Ann.*, 1840, 35, 24.
3. P. PFEIFFER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1940, 53, 93.
4. P. PFEIFFER, E. BUCHHOLZ and O. BAUER, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1931, 129, 163.
5. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.* 1966, 7, 83.
6. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1975, 54, 454.
7. V. B. MOHAN KUMAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 928.
8. H. S. VERTER and A. E. FROST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 85.
9. A. CHAKRAVORTY and R. H. HOLM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3999.
10. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 615.
11. V. B. MOHAN KUMAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, Communicated to *J. Coor. Chem.*

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12. ULMANN and GOLDBERG, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 2811.
13. A. EAENSHSW, "Introduction to Magnetochemistry", Academic Press New York, 1964, p. 35.
14. H. S. FRENCH, M. Z. MAGGE and E. SCHEFFIELD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1924.
15. L. SACCONI, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1968, **4**, 211.
16. D. P. GRADDON and K. M. MOCKLER, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 21.
17. L. SACCONI, P. PAOLETTI and R. CINI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3583.
18. R. H. HOLM and M. J. O'CONNOR, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 252.
19. L. SACCONI, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1968, **4**, 269.
20. R. H. HOLM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4683.